

DOXORUBICIN AND GEMCITABINE IN CANCER THERAPY: CLASSIFICATION, MECHANISMS, LIMITATIONS, AND MODERN DELIVERY APPROACHES

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Abstract. *This article examines the current classification of chemotherapeutic agents and the role of Doxorubicin and Gemcitabine in oncology therapy. The mechanisms of action, therapeutic efficacy, and major limitations of these drugs are analyzed, including nonspecific toxicity and the development of drug resistance in tumor cells. Particular attention is given to modern approaches aimed at reducing adverse effects, such as targeted drug delivery systems and the use of nanocarriers that enable selective accumulation of chemotherapeutic agents in tumor tissue. Furthermore, the prospects for the development of chemotherapy are discussed, including combination treatment regimens and personalized therapeutic strategies designed to improve clinical outcomes and safety. This study emphasizes the importance of further research to optimize the therapeutic application of doxorubicin and gemcitabine in cancer treatment.*

Keywords: *doxorubicin, Gemcitabine, Targeted drug delivery, Nanocarriers, Controlled drug delivery.*

1. Introduction. Currently, there is a global trend toward an increasing incidence of cancer worldwide (WHO & IARC, 2024). There are numerous approaches to suppress the disease, such as surgical intervention, radiation therapy and immunotherapy, among which chemotherapy remains one of the key treatment methods and is widely used both as a standalone approach and as part of combination therapy regimens (Wang & Jing, 2025). Chemotherapeutic treatment makes it possible to reduce tumor size, destroy cancer cells, prevent the risk of recurrence, exert systemic effects on metastases, and enable the treatment of tumors in various locations, as well as eliminate very small malignant cells that cannot yet be detected even with the use of the most advanced diagnostic methods (Litvinets, Zakharova, & Sukhova, 2024;).

The modern classification of chemotherapeutic agents organizes them according to their mechanism of action, spectrum of application, and toxicity profile, which allows for the comparison of the efficacy and safety of different drugs. Prominent representatives among chemotherapeutic agents include doxorubicin and gemcitabine, which retain their clinical significance due to their proven antitumor activity, broad spectrum of use in various types of malignant tumors, and high efficacy both as monotherapy and as part of combination treatment regimens (Khan, Agarwal, Assaad, Ratan, & Nassif Haddad, 2026). These drugs remain the standard of care due to the accumulated data on their safety, predictable side effect profile, and the possibility of their use in neoadjuvant, adjuvant, and palliative treatment settings (Anwar, Husain, Bilal, Ijaz, Aadil, & Khan, 2024).

However, despite all the advantages of these drugs, they also have certain limitations, including the development of tumor drug resistance, limited efficacy of chemotherapy in certain tumor localizations, as well as adverse effects such as cardiotoxicity, myelosuppression,

gastrointestinal disorders, alopecia, and an increased risk of infectious complications (Gaumond, Lee, Warp, Kamholtz, Dreifus, & Jimenez, 2025). Based on these findings, significant attention is currently being paid to reducing the undesirable effects of cytotoxic drugs, and numerous studies are being conducted to achieve their targeted delivery and selective action.

Thus, the search for effective approaches to increase selectivity and reduce the toxicity of chemotherapeutic agents remains an important objective of modern oncology. The aim of this study is to analyze the challenges and prospects of using doxorubicin and gemcitabine in contemporary anticancer therapy.

2. Modern classification of chemotherapeutic agents

Chemotherapeutic drugs act through two pathways: cytostatic and cytotoxic. The cytostatic pathway inhibits the proliferation of malignant cells and induces apoptosis. Cytotoxic chemotherapy directly kills cells by disrupting their vital functions, resulting in tumor necrosis. Antitumor drugs used in chemotherapy can be divided into several groups based on their structure and mode of action.

2.1 Alkylating agents

Alkylating anticancer chemotherapeutic agents have the ability to form covalent bonds with nucleophilic centers of DNA (most commonly the nitrogen atom at position 7, guanine) (MDPI, 2021), which in turn causes inter- and intra-strand cross-links of the DNA molecule, resulting in disruption of replication and transcription processes, which induces tumor cell apoptosis. Alkylating agents are not phase-specific and exhibit greatest activity in rapidly dividing cells. These include cyclophosphamide, carmustine, cisplatin, carboplatin, dacarbazine, chlorambucil, and oxaliplatin. They have found clinical application in tumor types such as lymphomas and leukemias, breast cancer, sarcomas, ovarian tumors, head and neck tumors, and gliomas. Side effects include nephrotoxicity (cisplatin), neurotoxicity, myelosuppression (more pronounced with carboplatin), immunodepression, hemorrhagic cystitis (associated with acrolein), alopecia, nausea and vomiting (Chiorcea-Paquim & Oliveira-Brett, 2023).

2.2 Antimetabolites

Antimetabolites interfere with the synthesis of vital cellular components, such as inhibiting DNA and RNA production by taking the place of nucleotides. In other words, antimetabolites are molecules that compete with metabolites (vital substances). By competing with natural substrates, they inhibit nucleotide synthesizing enzymes (for example, methotrexate inhibits dehydrofolate reductase, blocking the synthesis of tetrahydrofolate, which is necessary for the formation of thymidylate (dTMP), thus disrupting DNA synthesis (Rana, Dranchak, Inglese, et al., 2024)) or are incorporated into DNA in place of nucleotides (5-fluorouracil (5-FU), gemcitabine, and cytarabine are incorporated into DNA or RNA, causing replication errors, chain arrest, and apoptosis). Antimetabolites are particularly active in the S phase of the cell cycle, when DNA synthesis occurs. Rapidly dividing cells, including tumor cells, bone marrow, and gastrointestinal epithelial tissue, are most sensitive to antimetabolites. They are used to treat the following tumors: acute lymphoblastic leukemia, breast cancer, gastric cancer, pancreatic cancer (gemcitabine), colorectal cancer (5-FU), and acute myeloid leukemia (cytarabine). Side effects include myelosuppression, stomatitis, nausea, hepatotoxicity, alopecia, and neuropathy. Notable examples include 5-fluorouracil, 6-mercaptopurine, capecitabine, gemcitabine, and methotrexate.

2.3 Antitumor antibiotics

Antineoplastic antibiotics are produced by biosynthesis from microorganisms. Their mechanism of action involves intercalation into DNA, disrupting its structure and interfering with

replication and transcription, and blocking enzymes such as topoisomerase II (Karamanolis, Kounatidis, Vallianou, Dimitriou, Tsaroucha, Tsioulos, Anastasiou, Mavrothalassitis, Karampela, & Dalamaga, 2024). Antibiotics also generate free radicals: in the presence of oxygen and transition metals, some antibiotics (e.g., anthracyclines) induce the formation of reactive oxygen species, resulting in damage to DNA and cellular structures. They are used to treat lymphomas, leukemia, soft tissue sarcomas, and solid tumors. Their classes include: anthracyclines (cardiotoxicity (Lozhkina & Spiridonov, 2021; Graziani et al., 2026), myelosuppression), actinomycin (myelosuppression, mucosal toxicity), bleomycin (pulmonary toxicity, fibrosis, skin reactions), and mitomycin (myelosuppression, organ toxicity). Anthracyclines include doxorubicin (adriamycin), epirubicin, daunorubicin, and idarubicin.

2.4 Proteasome inhibitors

Proteasome inhibitors block the function of proteasomes, which regulate cellular protein homeostasis, remove damaged and short-lived proteins, and regulate cell apoptosis. Inhibition of proteasome function results in an increase in defective proteins and induction of cell death. They are used primarily for multiple myeloma and lymphoma. Side effects include peripheral neuropathy, thrombocytopenia, gastrointestinal disturbances, increased risk of infection, cardiotoxicity, hypertension, dyspnea, and nephrotoxicity. Representatives of this group include cartelzamib, ixazomib, and bortezomib (Pakjoo, Ahmadi, Zahedi, et al., 2024).

2.5 Plant alkaloids

Alkaloids and their derivatives are substances obtained from plants. The primary target of this group of drugs is the mitotic center of the cell. These substances interact with microtubule tubulin, disrupting their polymerization processes and blocking the cell cycle primarily in the G2/M phase, ultimately inducing tumor cell apoptosis. They are used to treat leukemia, sarcomas, ovarian cancer, prostate cancer, lung cancer, and lymphoma. Side effects include neurotoxicity, myelosuppression, alopecia, gastrointestinal disturbances, peripheral neuropathy, and hypersensitivity reactions. These include vinalkoloids, taxanes, and podophyllotoxins (Dehelean, Marcovici, Soica, Mioc, Coricovac, Iurciuc, Cretu, & Pinzaru, 2021).

3. Doxorubicin in oncology therapy

As mentioned above, chemotherapy drugs are divided into several groups, including the anthracycline group. Anthracycline antibiotics disrupt the DNA of cancer cells, thereby stopping their cell division. A prominent example of this group is the antitumor drug doxorubicin.

3.1 Pharmacological characteristics

Doxorubicin is one of the most toxic drugs for cancer cells, although its effects also manifest in healthy cells (Radeva & Yoncheva, 2025). Doxorubicin is a red, crystalline powder. It is used exclusively as an intravenous solution. The structural formula of doxorubicin, as shown in Figure 1, is a tetracyclic ring of doxorubicinone linked by a glycosidic bond to the amino sugar daunosamine.

Figure 1. Structure of Doxorubicin

<https://www.rlsnet.ru/active-substance/doksorubicin-51>

3.2 Mechanism of action

Doxorubicin is a drug with two modes of action, characteristic of its class of anthracycline antibiotics. I.

Doxorubicin's cytostatic action is accompanied by intercalation into the DNA strand, as can be seen in Figure 2, and inhibition of the enzyme topoisomerase II (Karamanolis et al., 2024). The mechanism of doxorubicin's cytostatic action begins with its insertion between DNA base pairs, which is accompanied by the destruction of the DNA helix, leading to disruption of replication and transcription processes. Subsequently, the cell becomes incapable of synthesizing DNA and RNA molecules, division ceases, and apoptosis is induced (Radeva & Yoncheva, 2025). Doxorubicin's mechanism of action, through inhibition of the enzyme topoisomerase II, is that this enzyme cuts and cross-links DNA strands to reduce coiling during replication. Doxorubicin, however, retains the enzyme at the DNA breakpoint, preventing the strand from rejoining. This causes double-strand breaks in DNA, leading to cell death.

Figure 2. Insertion of doxorubicin molecules between DNA strands

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Doxorubicin%E2%80%93DNA_complex_1D12.png?uselang=ru

II. The cytotoxic effect of doxorubicin is manifested by the release of free radicals and binding to membranes and lipids. Through reactions with iron ($\text{Fe}^{2+} \rightarrow \text{Fe}^{3+}$), doxorubicin is capable of forming reactive oxygen species, which damage DNA, proteins, and lipid membranes, resulting in oxidative stress and cell death. This mechanism of action of doxorubicin explains its high cardiotoxicity, since the heart is sensitive to oxidative damage (Radeva & Yoncheva, 2025). Doxorubicin can also interact with cell membranes, namely phospholipids. This can alter membrane fluidity and affect ion channel transport.

3.3 Spectrum of clinical application

This multidirectional action of Doxorubicin explains its effectiveness against both rapidly and moderately proliferating tumors, as well as its use in the treatment of a wide range of malignant neoplasms, such as hematological (acute lymphomas, leukemia, myelomas), solid (breast cancer, soft tissue and bone sarcomas, ovarian and endometrial cancer, lung cancer (small cell), bladder cancer, thyroid tumors, hepatocellular carcinoma) (Mahboubi, Almasi-Hashiani, Ghasemi, & Mondanizadeh, 2025).

3.4 Limitations of therapy

Despite high efficacy and toxicity to cancer cells, chemotherapy with doxorubicin does have an impact on healthy cells. Doxorubicin has numerous side effects that leave a profound impact on the body:

1. The main side effect is cardiotoxicity. This is the most serious and dose-dependent effect. Myocardial cells are damaged due to the formation of reactive oxygen species, interaction with iron ($\text{Fe}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+}$), and inhibition of topoisomerase II β in cardiomyocytes. Consequences can include dilated cardiomyopathy (the ventricles dilate and lose their ability to effectively pump blood) and heart failure. For protection, dexrazoxane, a drug that binds iron, reduces cellular oxidative stress, is used (Graziani et al., 2026).

2. Myelosuppression – suppression of bone marrow function and a decrease in the level of formed elements of the blood: leukocytes (leukopenia), platelets (thrombocytopenia), and erythrocytes (anemia). This increases the risk of infections and bleeding.

3. Gastrointestinal reactions are accompanied by nausea, vomiting, and loss of appetite. Mucositis – inflammation of the mucous membranes (especially the oral cavity) – is also observed.

4. Alopecia – almost all patients experience hair loss during treatment, but this process is reversible after completion of therapy.

5. Extravasation – leakage from a vein during drug administration. If the drug enters a vessel, severe tissue necrosis occurs. Therefore, doxorubicin is administered only intravenously, with careful monitoring of the injection site.

6. Hepatotoxicity – increased levels of ALT and AST transaminases (protein transporters). In severe cases, this can lead to liver dysfunction.

7. Another adverse effect of the drug is the development of secondary tumors. For example, leukemia caused by DNA damage (topoisomerase II) is possible. This is rare and only occurs if therapy has been ongoing for many years.

Due to the large number of side effects, doxorubicin remains an important subject of research in targeted medicine, where the combination of antitumor drugs with various carriers or targeting agents enables significantly improved therapeutic outcomes.

4. Gemcitabine in oncology therapy

Another class of antitumor drugs widely used in chemotherapy is the class of antimetabolite drugs. Antimetabolites exhibit cytostatic activity, which is expressed by altering the structure of the cell's genetic apparatus, leading to cell apoptosis. One of the representatives of the antimetabolite group is the drug gemcitabine, which has found wide application in the fight against many types of tumors.

4.1 Pharmacological characteristics

Gemcitabine is a white powder intended for intravenous administration. In the body, it is metabolized primarily in the liver and kidneys by cytidine deaminase into mono-, di-, and triphosphate metabolites (dFdCMP, dFdCDP, and dFdCTP). Among these, the di- and triphosphate forms are the active cytotoxic metabolites that inhibit DNA synthesis during the S phase of the cell cycle. The drug is primarily excreted by the kidneys in the urine, with an elimination half-life of approximately 5–11 hours (Vidal, n.d.).

4.2 Mechanism of action

Gemcitabine is a cytotoxic drug that belongs to the class of antimetabolites, specifically pyrimidine analogs. Metabolites are substances involved in the body's metabolic processes, such as amino acids, nucleotides, sugars, and others. In contrast, antimetabolites are structurally similar to natural metabolites but interfere with normal biochemical processes within the cell. As one of these agents, gemcitabine competes with pyrimidine bases, particularly deoxycytidine (Dash, Honda, Komuro, Okada, Sugisawa, & Ueda, 2024). As shown in Figure 3, the structural difference

between deoxycytidine and gemcitabine lies in the presence of two fluorine atoms in the gemcitabine molecule, which are responsible for its altered biological activity and antitumor properties.

Figure 3. Comparison of the chemical structures of gemcitabine (left) and deoxycytidine (right)

(<https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/thumb/a/a3/Desoxycytidin.svg/463px-Desoxycytidin.svg.png>)

Gemcitabine is phosphorylated intracellularly by nucleoside kinases to form active nucleotide metabolites, including gemcitabine monophosphate (dFdCMP), gemcitabine diphosphate (dFdCDP), and gemcitabine triphosphate (dFdCTP). Gemcitabine exhibits phase specificity, primarily affecting cells in the S and G1/S phases of the cell cycle. During the S phase, DNA replication occurs through the action of various enzymes. At this stage, gemcitabine diphosphate binds to ribonucleotide reductase, an enzyme responsible for converting ribonucleotides into deoxyribonucleotides, and forms an irreversible covalent complex with it. As a result, gemcitabine diphosphate inhibits ribonucleotide reductase activity, preventing the formation of normal deoxyribonucleotides required for DNA synthesis.

This leads to depletion of intracellular deoxyribonucleotide pools, inhibition of DNA synthesis, and disruption of cell cycle progression, ultimately triggering apoptosis. In addition, the active triphosphate form of gemcitabine (dFdCTP) is incorporated into the growing DNA strand in place of deoxycytidine during DNA replication, causing premature chain termination. Consequently, DNA synthesis is disrupted, leading to apoptotic death of tumor cells (Nemati, Hsu, Nathiya, Kumar, Oghenemaro, Kariem, Kaur, Bhanot, Hjazi, & Saedi, 2025).

4.3 Clinical application

Gemcitabine is used to treat many types of cancer, including testicular cancer, breast cancer, non-small cell lung cancer, ovarian cancer, pancreatic cancer, and bladder cancer. It is also used alone, for example, in the palliative stage of the disease or in elderly patients. Gemcitabine can also be used in combination with drugs such as paclitaxel, carboplatin, and cisplatin, for greater effectiveness (Huang, Hung, Tsai, Wu, Chou, Hsu, Yeh, Chen, Wang, & Yeh, 2024).

4.4 Limitations of therapy

Like all cytostatic drugs, gemcitabine has side effects. Adverse effects include the following:

1. Leukopenia, thrombocytopenia, and anemia are the main limiting toxic effects, which severely damage the hematological system.
2. Nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite, stomatitis, and oral ulcers. These symptoms often occur during chemotherapy and should be controlled with supportive care. Oral mucosal

cells divide rapidly, and gemcitabine, by inhibiting their renewal, promotes inflammatory processes, which are accompanied by sore throats, pain, and difficulty eating.

3. Fever, weakness, fatigue, chills, and muscle aches. These symptoms may be intermittent and related to the drug.

4. Liver toxicity (increased ALT, AST, and alkaline phosphatase). Typically, the changes are moderate and reversible.

5. Rash, itching, severe skin reactions, alopecia. These side effects occur in slightly rare cases.

6. Pulmonary complications – interstitial pneumonitis.

7. Fluid retention, swelling of the face and extremities, weakness. These adverse effects are observed in a minority of patients.

8. Neuropathy, numbness, pins and needles, headaches, seizures. These side effects occur as a result of the negative effects of gemcitabine on the body's nervous system.

9. Gemcitabine can also lead to renal dysfunction, which manifests as renal failure, hemolysis-uremia syndrome, and thrombotic microangiopathy.

The large number of side effects associated with gemcitabine provides the basis for ongoing research aimed at reducing its toxicity and improving its selectivity toward tumor cells.

5. Approaches to reducing the adverse effects of chemotherapeutic agents

The side effects of chemotherapy are primarily caused by its nonspecific cytotoxic effects on rapidly proliferating normal cells, including bone marrow cells, gastrointestinal epithelium, hair follicles, and other tissues (Cronin et al., 2026; Yang et al., 2026). Therefore, various strategies have been developed to improve the selectivity of anticancer therapy and protect healthy tissues, among which targeted therapy represents one of the most promising approaches currently available. The principle of targeted therapy is based on the selective accumulation of therapeutic agents in tumor tissue while minimizing their impact on healthy organs. The key factors in effective drug targeting include the selection of an appropriate delivery strategy—either passive or active targeting—the mechanisms of cellular uptake and intracellular retention, as well as the choice of suitable drug carriers.

5.1 Passive targeting of Doxorubicin

Due to its pronounced systemic toxicity, doxorubicin has been extensively investigated for targeted delivery applications. Passive accumulation of drugs in tumor tissue occurs via the enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect, which is associated with the unique structural characteristics of tumor vasculature. Tumor blood vessels exhibit increased permeability and enlarged intercellular gaps due to rapid and abnormal angiogenesis, enabling preferential accumulation of macromolecules and nanocarriers within tumor tissue (Fang, Nakamura, & Maeda, 2025) (Figure 4).

This effect operates only for macromolecules or nanoparticles (10–200 nm), whereas doxorubicin, being a small hydrophilic molecule (~580 Da), is not able to be retained in tumor tissue for a long time and is rapidly metabolized and eliminated from the body. Therefore, numerous studies have been conducted aimed at increasing the effective size of the doxorubicin molecule and its encapsulation into nanocontainers. One of such nanocontainers is liposomes, which, due to their spherical structure surrounded by a lipid bilayer, serve as a model of the cellular membrane (Bozzuto & Molinari, 2025). DOX is encapsulated inside liposomes, within their hydrophilic core, which protects the drug from degradation in the bloodstream, reduces systemic toxicity, prolongs circulation time, and enhances accumulation in tumor tissue via the EPR effect.

In addition, studies have investigated the incorporation of the polymer polyethylene glycol (PEG) into liposomes, which “coats” the liposome surface and increases circulation time in the blood. As a result, liposomes are less readily recognized and taken up by macrophages of the liver and spleen, exhibit reduced immunogenicity by masking them from the immune system, and demonstrate improved passive accumulation via the EPR effect. DOXIL was the first PEGylated liposomal formulation of DOX approved by the FDA in 1995 and became the first nanomedicine in oncology, significantly reducing cardiotoxicity and improving drug distribution.

Enhanced Permeability and Retention (EPR) Effect

Figure 4. EPR effect

Modern studies continue to optimize the DOXIL formulation by introducing targeting ligands, new co-loading strategies, and stimulus-responsive modifications to improve therapeutic efficacy. One study reported, for the first time, the simultaneous loading of two drugs—DOX and hydralazine (HDZ)—into liposomes using a pH-gradient technique. In vitro studies in breast cancer cell lines (MCF7 and MDA-MB-231) demonstrated high cytotoxicity toward tumor cells and significantly lower toxicity toward normal cells, highlighting the potential of this system for combination cancer therapy (Alshaer, Lafi, Nsairat, AlQuaissi, Alqudah, Zureigat, & Hamad, 2025).

In addition to particle size and the EPR effect, stimulus-responsive properties of nanoparticles are also important, as they enable condition-specific drug release. In one study, redox-responsive liposomes encapsulating DOX were developed. These liposomes showed stability under normal physiological conditions but selectively released the drug under intracellular oxidative-reductive (redox) stress conditions characteristic of tumor tissue. It was demonstrated that this modification enhances DOX delivery into tumor cells due to elevated glutathione (GSH) levels and results in improved antitumor activity both in vitro and in vivo compared to conventional liposomes (Mirhadi, Ramezani, Atyabi, & Dinarvand, 2022).

The next type of DOX carriers is polymeric micelles, which, in contrast to liposomes, possess smaller sizes, increased stability in the bloodstream, and broad possibilities for chemical modification (Kwon & Kataoka, 2024). Micelles are nanostructures, typically 10–100 nm in size, that self-assemble from amphiphilic polymers in an aqueous environment. Micelles consist of a

hydrophobic core, where drugs including DOX (in free or modified form) can be incorporated or conjugated, and a hydrophilic shell composed of polymers, most commonly polyethylene glycol (PEG) (Cabral & Kataoka, 2025).

Studies have focused on the controlled release of DOX, in which the drug is covalently conjugated via a pH-sensitive Schiff base linkage that is cleaved in acidic environments characteristic of tumor tissue. Experimental results have shown that such nanoparticles exhibit good stability, increased intracellular DOX concentration, and improved antitumor activity compared with free DOX *in vitro* (Li, 2023).

To enhance therapeutic efficacy in breast cancer treatment, researchers have developed pH-sensitive polymeric micelles capable of simultaneously delivering two anticancer drugs—DOX and docetaxel. *In vivo* studies in mice bearing 4T1 tumors demonstrated that the combined delivery system achieved greater tumor accumulation and more effective tumor growth inhibition. Additionally, reduced accumulation in the heart was observed compared with the free drug combination, suggesting a potential reduction in cardiotoxicity (Farhoudi, Hosseinihah, Kazemi-Beydokhti, Arabi, Alavizadeh, Moosavian, & Jaafari, 2024).

5.2 Active targeting of Doxorubicin

In active targeting, drugs are modified with specific targeting moieties that recognize receptors or molecules on the surface of tumor cells. This approach increases intracellular drug concentration in tumor tissue, reduces systemic side effects, and allows the use of lower doses while maintaining therapeutic efficacy (Danhier, Feron, & Préat, 2025). Targeting moieties include ligands, antibodies, aptamers, peptides, and others.

An experimental study reported the development of CD147 antibody-modified nanoparticle prodrugs. DOX was first conjugated with oxidized dextrin (ODEX) via a Schiff base linkage, forming a nanoprodrug. Subsequently, anti-CD147 antibodies (a liver cancer marker) were attached to the nanoparticle surface. The results demonstrated pH-sensitive release of DOX, enhanced tumor accumulation, and significant inhibition of HepG2 hepatoma growth in experimental models (Tian, Yu, Zhang, He, Sun, & Ni, 2023).

Another experimental development involved an antibody–drug conjugate, PD0721–DOX. PD0721 is a single-chain variable fragment antibody (scFv) specific to EGFRvIII (epidermal growth factor receptor variant III, commonly overexpressed in glioblastoma). When conjugated with DOX via a dextran-based linker, the system effectively recognized EGFRvIII-expressing cells and was internalized by them, resulting in increased apoptotic activity against glioblastoma cells *in vitro* (Hu, Liu, Zhang, Lu, Zheng, Wang, Chen, & Liu, 2024).

In addition, studies have demonstrated enhanced therapeutic efficacy using combination approaches. In one study, DOX was conjugated to polydopamine (PDA) nanoparticles via a Schiff base reaction, and the nanoparticle surface was further modified with an RGD peptide to actively target integrins overexpressed on tumor cells. *In vitro* results showed a strong antitumor effect through combined chemo- and photothermal therapy, while *in vivo* studies demonstrated significant tumor accumulation and tumor growth inhibition without notable systemic toxicity (Yuan, Lu, Xu, & Liu, 2024).

5.3 Passive targeting of Gemcitabine

Gemcitabine, due to the hydrophilic nature of its molecule, which contributes to its rapid metabolism in the body (it is deaminated to an inactive form) and short half-life, as well as its systemic toxicity, has become an important subject of research for encapsulation into nanocarriers. This approach enables protection of Gemcitabine from rapid degradation, prolongation of its

circulation time in the bloodstream, increased tumor accumulation, and reduced toxicity to healthy tissues (Wang, Zhang, Zhang, Chen, & Li, 2025).

One study compared the cytotoxicity of liposomal Gemcitabine and free Gemcitabine solution in the A549 lung adenocarcinoma cell line *in vitro*. The results demonstrated that the liposomal formulation exhibited significantly higher activity ($IC_{50} \approx 0.47 \mu M$) against tumor cells compared to free Gemcitabine ($IC_{50} \approx 9.6 \mu M$), which was attributed to the improved cellular uptake of the liposomal form and its protection from premature degradation (Oborotov, Rudakova, Baryshnikova, Dmitrieva, & Krasnyuk, 2025).

Research is also underway on the development of thermosensitive liposomes, in which the membrane is engineered for temperature responsiveness by selecting the type of phospholipid, hydrocarbon chain length, degree of saturation, cholesterol content, and addition of lysolipids. In a recent study, thermosensitive liposomes were developed for the delivery of gemcitabine in pancreatic cancer. These liposomes remain stable at normal body temperature ($37^\circ C$), but under hyperthermia conditions ($43\text{--}45^\circ C$), the lipid bilayer transitions into a liquid-crystalline state, making the membrane more “fluid” and facilitating rapid drug release. The authors highlight the potential for controlled release and enhanced stability of gemcitabine using this approach (Aparicio-Lopez, Timmerman, Lorino, Rogers, Pyle, Shrestha, et al., 2024).

Since micelles are more compact and stable particles (allowing better penetration into dense tumors) and flexible for manipulations aimed at controlled release, they are more convenient for research compared with liposomes (Kujundziski & Chamovska, 2025). Due to the hydrophilic nature of the Gemcitabine molecule, when encapsulating it into the hydrophobic core of micelles, the drug is modified with hydrophobic moieties. For example, in one study, Gemcitabine was modified with vitamin E and encapsulated into the micelle core. Vitamin E serves not only as a modifying agent but also as an active component, enhancing the cytotoxic effect of Gemcitabine through synergistic action. The results demonstrated improved Gemcitabine stability in the bloodstream, higher tumor accumulation via the EPR effect, and reduced side effects compared to free Gemcitabine (Pereira-Silva, Miranda-Pastoriza, Diaz-Gomez, Sotelo, Paiva-Santos, Veiga, Concheiro, & Alvarez-Lorenzo, 2024).

Another study investigated Gemcitabine delivery using membrane-modified micelles. A coating of cancer cell membrane fragments was applied to the surface of micelles made from the synthetic polymer Soluplus, which masks the nanoparticles and facilitates recognition by tumor cells. This approach is referred to as biomimetic targeted delivery. The study provides evidence that membrane-modified Soluplus micelles loaded with Gemcitabine prodrug represent a promising delivery system for targeted therapy of pancreatic cancer (Pereira-Silva, Diaz-Gomez, Blanco-Fernandez, Ferreirós, Veiga, Concheiro, Paiva-Santos, & Alvarez-Lorenzo, 2024).

5.4 Active targeting of Gemcitabine

To enhance Gemcitabine accumulation in tumors, reduce its side effects, and increase therapeutic efficacy, Gemcitabine-based nanoparticles are modified with specific targeting moieties. For example, one study described the development of “smart” micelles for improved drug delivery with active targeting to cancer cells expressing the CD44 receptor. For targeting, a conjugate of hyaluronic acid and phospholipid (HA-DPPE) was incorporated. As a result, the micelles were selectively taken up by cells with high CD44 expression and exhibited high cytotoxicity in these cells (Andreana, Bincoletto, Ricci, Salaroglio, Manzoli, Zurletti, Milone, Rolando, Del Favero, Riganti, Matricardi, Stella, & Arpicco, 2025).

Active targeting of Gemcitabine has also been applied in combination therapies. For example, one study reported the development of self-assembled nanoparticles targeting the folate receptor (FR), which is frequently overexpressed on cancer cells. Gemcitabine was modified into an amphiphilic prodrug (DOG) and linked to γ -octadecyl folate (MOFA), a ligand that recognizes the folate receptor. Indocyanine green (ICG), a photosensitizer for combined chemo- and photothermal therapy, was also incorporated into the nanoparticles. The results showed high ICG loading efficiency (~74%), pH- and laser-triggered release of Gemcitabine, and enhanced antitumor activity with the combined chemo-photothermal treatment compared with chemotherapy alone (Kuang, Liu, Wang, Yang, Zeng, & Ming, 2023).

Therefore, the use of both passive and active targeting strategies for the delivery of anticancer drugs represents a promising approach to enhance the efficacy of chemotherapy. Passive tumor accumulation via the EPR effect can be further reinforced through ligand-mediated interactions with tumor cell receptors, enabling more precise and controlled delivery of cytotoxic agents.

6. Limitations and Future Perspectives

Despite significant advances in the application of DOX and Gemcitabine, current approaches have several limitations. Even with targeted carriers, it is not always possible to reach all tumor cells, particularly in dense or poorly vascularized tumors, and the development of drug resistance reduces therapeutic efficacy. In addition, pharmacokinetic and technological challenges remain, including the instability of some delivery systems and difficulties in scalable production.

Future prospects include the development of more stable and selective carriers, combination therapy regimens, and personalized approaches tailored to the molecular characteristics of individual tumors. Integrating these strategies with modern therapeutic modalities has the potential to significantly improve the clinical efficacy and safety of chemotherapy.

7. Conclusion

Modern classification of chemotherapeutic agents allows a systematic approach to therapy selection in oncology, taking into account mechanisms of action and drug toxicity. DOX and Gemcitabine remain key drugs in the treatment of various tumor types due to their proven efficacy; however, their use is limited by nonspecific toxicity and the development of drug resistance. The development of targeted delivery systems and novel carriers enables increased selectivity and reduced side effects, opening new prospects for safer and more effective therapy. Overall, continued research and optimization of drug delivery strategies and combination regimens are essential for improving clinical outcomes and advancing personalized treatment for patients with cancer.

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